

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R7.8 Feasibility study on applicability of seismic methods for CO₂ plume monitoring

Authors: Roman Pevzner, Boris Gurevich
(Perth, WA, Australia)

November 2023

CONTENT

FOREWORD	3
1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
2 INTRODUCTION	4
3 PLUME GEOMETRY FROM FLOW SIMULATIONS	5
4 ROCK PHYSICS MODELLING	7
4.1 Model of baseline properties at the virtual well location.....	7
4.2 Define properties of fluids and rock.....	8
4.3 Fluid replacement for each time step	10
5 SEISMIC SIMULATIONS	10
5.1 Seismic simulations – surface and VSP geometries	12
5.2 Zero-offset and offset VSP geometries	13
5.3 Walk-away VSP geometry	16
5.4 Surface seismic	18
Zero-offset VSP data processing to simulate surface seismic response	18
5.5 Feasibility of the cross-hole seismic option	24
6 DISCUSSION	27
6.1 Simulation, not prediction	27
6.2 Surface seismic vs vertical seismic profiling, limitations of the 1.5D approach	28
6.3 Potential hardware realisations and acquisition geometries, intervention vs PRM.....	29
6.4 Time-lapse cross-hole surveys	30
7 CONCLUSION	30
REFERENCES	31

FOREWORD

“To be able to assess the applicability of seismic survey - the most powerful monitoring tool for mapping the extension of the CO₂ plume in the subsurface, a feasibility study will be performed. The study will use the existing seismic data from the site and the available geological and petrophysical information, and combine them with forward modelling and creation of synthetic seismograms. Various seismic techniques like surface 3D, VSP (incl. 3D VSP) or cross-hole will be evaluated. The study will be subcontracted; results will be reported in R7.8.” (according to the project document named Detailed Description of Work Packages of the CO₂-SPICER project). As a result of competitive tendering, Mr. Roman Pevzner (Perth, Australia) has been chosen as subcontractor for this feasibility study.

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Seismic monitoring plays an important role in the CCUS MMV program as it provides good spatial resolution and is sensitive to changes in pore fluid. This report aims to evaluate the detectability of CO₂ in the Zarosice field using a desktop study based on a combination of flow simulations, rock physics and seismic modelling.

We simulate seismic response on the grid of seismic sources and receivers, which would be suitable for evaluating surface and downhole geometry. Then, we perform time-lapse data analysis to evaluate the level of time-lapse data and decide on the detectability of the plume using different acquisition geometries based on the previous experience with the repeatability of each method.

The feasibility study of seismic monitoring in the Zarosice field allowed us to arrive at the following conclusions:

- Surface seismic monitoring of the CO₂ injection into the depleted oil and gas reservoir has limited chances of imaging the plume because of the small time-lapse signal level. However, surface seismic might be used to conduct assurance monitoring (absence of leakage in the overburden);
- Borehole seismic is likely to be useful in detecting and imaging the plume (because of the higher degree of repeatability); DAS receivers are the preferred option;
- A combination of offset VSPs (potentially with permanent sources) and 4D VSP are the preferred set of geometries;
- Application of cross-hole time-lapse seismic technique is feasible. However, the primary motivation to use it is likely related to imaging the plume using reflected waves rather than travel time tomography.

2 INTRODUCTION

Seismic monitoring plays an important role in the Carbon Capture, Utilization and Storage Measuring, Monitoring and Verification (CCUS MMV) programme as it provides good spatial resolution and is sensitive to changes in pore fluid (Lumley 2010). It can be applied for both conformance and assurance monitoring. Conformance monitoring is broadly defined as the possibility of tracking the propagation of the plume inside the primary containment to confirm its' behaviour matches the project goals. Assurance monitoring means the possibility of detecting various adverse effects, such as CO₂ leakage outside of the containment or excessive induced seismicity.

Seismic monitoring can be conducted using several different approaches. Active surface 4D seismic allows us to obtain the full 3D image of the evolving plume and potentially detect leakages. It was successfully applied in a number of commercial (Phythian et al. 2023, Eiken et al. 2011) and demonstration or research projects, such as the CO₂CRC Otway project (Pevzner et al. 2017), Ketzin (Ivandić et al. 2015). The utilisation of the permanent receiver arrays allows for a considerable reduction in the degree of invasiveness and improvement of repeatability of the surveys (Jervis et al. 2018, Pevzner et al. 2017).

Downhole seismic uses several different acquisition techniques. Conventional offset VSP geometry was reported to be useful for both detection of the plume (Tertyshnikov et al. 2017) and detailed evaluation of the changes of elastic properties through FWI (Egorov et al. 2017) or other techniques (Al Hosni et al. 2016). Walk away and 4D VSP we deployed to monitor CO₂ injection in a number of projects, including Aquistor (Harris 2017, White et al. 2019), Otway (Yurikov et al. 2022, AlNasser et al. 2017), Decatur (Couëslan et al. 2014), CSIRO In-Situ lab (Michael et al. 2020), CaMI (Lawton et al. 2017) and other projects. Note that both conventional geophones and fibre optic cables via distributed acoustic sensing technology were successfully used for these purposes.

Application cross-hole seismic technology was reported for Cranfield (Ajo-Franklin et al. 2013), Nagaoka (Saito et al. 2006) and other projects, including cases where it was used to monitor CO₂ injection in one of the reef formations (Gupta et al. 2020).

This report aims to evaluate the detectability of CO₂ in the Zarusice field in the reservoir using active time-lapse seismic surveys. We focus on conformance monitoring scenarios only and do not consider leakage of the CO₂ outside of the reservoir. To achieve this, we perform a desktop study based on a combination of flow simulations, rock physics and seismic modelling.

The general workflow includes the following steps:

- Initially, we analyse the likely plume geometry from the flow simulations
- Then, we identify the location for the synthetic well to perform rock physics modelling
- The results of the rock physics modelling will be used to generate a series of elastic models, which we'll utilise for 1.5D modelling.

The specifics of the Zarosice field is in the fact that it is an oil and gas field, and the injection of CO₂ will coincide with this hydrocarbon production.

We simulate seismic response on the grid of seismic sources and receivers, which would be suitable for evaluating surface and downhole geometry. Then, we perform time-lapse data analysis to evaluate the level of time-lapse data and decide on the detectability of the plume using different acquisition geometries based on the previous experience with the repeatability of each method.

3 PLUME GEOMETRY FROM FLOW SIMULATIONS

The overall configuration of the reservoir at the end of injection is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: CO₂ saturation at the end of the injection

To define the likely geometry of the plume, we use the following criteria:

- Initially, the cell would have less than 2% of free gas
- CO₂ saturation is greater than 10%

Plume thickness maps are provided Figure 2. The plume is increasing from ~100x100 m in three months from the start of the injection to 200 x 400 m in size at the end of the injection. Plume thickness can reach up to 35 m (away from the injector, ZA7 well). The size of the plume with significant thickness (>10-15 m) does not exceed 200 x 200 m.

A red asterisk on the same maps indicates the location of the synthetic well we will use for rock physics modelling and seismic simulations; the. The reason to opt for the synthetic well is the fact that all the real wells are either located in the area with thin plume or, as ZA7, not representative as the CO₂ column does not extend far away from the well.

Figure 2: Plume thickness maps

4 ROCK PHYSICS MODELLING

4.1 Model of baseline properties at the virtual well location

As discussed in the previous section, the modelling was done for a synthetic well called ZAN, which is located in a thick part of the CO₂ plume. The baseline properties for the synthetic well were modified from ZA7. The ZA7 was selected as a reference because the porosity profile in the flow model and baseline fluid distribution at the ZAN location are similar to those at the ZA7 well location (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Porosity and baseline fractions of water (blue), oil (green) and gas (red) in ZA7 (left) and ZAN (right)

However, the well logs from ZA7 were adjusted in two ways:

1. The reservoir section logs were shifted upwards by 108 meters to account for the difference in the reservoir top (1860 in ZA7 versus 1752 in ZAN). This shift was applied by reducing the thickness of a thick and relatively homogeneous shale layer about the reservoir at a depth of 1600 m.
2. The baseline fluid distributions at the ZAN location contained a small gas saturation of 2.5% within the top reservoir layer and exactly 1% (!) in the oil leg (Figure 4). We think at least this exactly 1% saturation across several grid cells is probably a simulation artefact. Furthermore, in the simulations, these gas saturation values vary with time, which may result in a spurious time-lapse signal unrelated to CO₂. In any case, since ZA7 contains no gas, the use of sonic and density logs from ZA7 for ZAN would be inconsistent with the presence of gas. For these reasons, we decided to modify the saturation values at ZAN by reducing the initial (baseline) gas saturation to zero.

Figure 4: Evolution of fractions of water (blue), oil (green), gas (red) and CO₂ (yellow) at the ZAN location from flow simulations

Once the baseline properties have been defined, we need to perform fluid substitution for all subsequent times. As the goal of this modelling is to obtain an estimate of the magnitude and character of the time-lapse signal rather than its precise shape, and since the input parameters are known only approximately, it makes sense to make simplifying assumptions and approximations. Fluid substitution consists of several steps.

4.2 Define properties of fluids and rock

For brine, in the absence of specific information about brine composition, we used properties of pure water (density 1000 kg/m³, bulk modulus 2.25 GPa). While the density

and bulk modulus of the formation brine is higher (brine density is 1020 kg/m³ at ambient conditions), the effect of the difference of the brine properties from fresh water is small and definitely smaller than uncertainties of other parameters, especially properties of live oil, see below.

Gas was assumed to be an ideal gas. For an ideal gas, the bulk modulus approximately equals reservoir fluid pressure, which was computed using Archimedes law for brine (assuming gas is normally pressured and resides below a brine column).

Calculation of the properties of in-situ oil is more involved. First, density of the live oil was taken from the slides provided (ZA7.pptx) as 0.85 g/cm³. The report gives reservoir temperature of 51°C, reservoir pressure of $P = 15.5$ MPa and API gravity of 24.4. The gas gravity factor G was taken as 0.56 assuming that gas dissolved in oil is mostly methane (Batzle and Wang (1992), page 1397), and the R_G factor was taken to be 30 adjusted to fit the reported density of live oil.

With these parameters, the V_p in the dead oil and its reference density were calculated using equations (20b) and (14) of Batzle and Wang (1992), respectively:

$$V_p = 15450(77.1 + API)^{-1/2} - 3.7T + 4.64P + 0.0115(0.36API^{1/2} - 1)TP \quad (1)$$

and

$$API = \frac{141.5}{\rho_0} - 131.5, \quad (2)$$

where T is temperature in °C and ρ_0 is reference density (measured at 15.6°C and atmospheric pressure. Then the properties of the live oil were calculated using equations (23) and (22) of Batzle and Wang (1992):

$$B_0 = 0.972 + 0.00038[2.4R_G(G/\rho_0)^{1/2} + T + 17.8]^{1.175} \quad (3)$$

and

$$\rho' = \frac{\rho_0}{B_0}(1 + 0.001R_G)^{-1} \quad (4)$$

as well as equations (1) and (2), now used with the parameters of live oil.

For CO₂, which at the reservoir conditions will be supercritical, density was taken to be 0.65 g/cm³, computed from density of pure CO₂ injected in Stage 2B of the Otway Project adjusted for temperature difference (62.4C at Otway vs 51.4C at Zarosice). The bulk modulus of CO₂ of 0.05 GPa was taken the same as for Otway parameters, which was, in turn, obtained from GERG thermodynamic model (Kunz and Group 2007).

The fluid mixture was assumed to be uniform, and thus its compressibility K_f^{-1} and density ρ_f were computed as weighted averages of the respective properties of the components.

As S-wave logs are not available, V_S was computed from V_p using Brocher's empirical equation for carbonate rocks (Mavko et al. (2009), equation (7.8.6)

$$V_S = 0.7858 - 1.2344V_p + 0.7949V_p^2 - 0.1238V_p^3 + 0.0064V_p^4. \quad (5)$$

Computed V_S as well as V_P and density before CO₂ injection are shown in Figure 5.

Then, the in-situ shear modulus μ and bulk modulus K were calculated from V_P , V_S and density ρ using standard equations

$$\mu = \rho V_S^2, \quad K = \rho V_P^2 - \frac{4}{3}\mu. \quad (6)$$

4.3 Fluid replacement for each time step

The next step was to perform Gassmann fluid substitution. This was done in two steps. First, the drained bulk modulus was computed using the inverse Gassmann equation (Zhu and McMechan 1990)

$$K_{DR} = \frac{K_{BASE} \left(\frac{\phi K_m}{K_f} + 1 - \phi \right) - K_m}{\frac{\phi K_m}{K_f} + \frac{K_{BASE}}{K_m} - 1 - \phi} \quad (7)$$

where ϕ is porosity, K_{BASE} is the undrained bulk modulus of the rock at baseline conditions, K_f is bulk modulus of the fluid mixture at baseline conditions, and K_m is bulk modulus of the mineral, taken to be 95 GPa (assuming dolomite as the dominant mineral). However, for very low porosities, the result of the calculation using equation (7) becomes too sensitive to errors in well logs. Thus, for porosities below 0.02 or in-situ bulk modulus larger than $0.995K_m$, the K_{DR} was taken equal K_m . In accordance with the Gassmann theory, the drained shear modulus is taken equal to the undrained shear modulus.

Then for each time step, the fluid mixture modulus K_{fM} and density are computed from saturation values taken from flow simulations as described in the above subsection. This computed fluid mixture bulk modulus is then used in the Gassmann equation

$$K_M = K_{DR} + \frac{\left(1 - \frac{K_{DR}}{K_m}\right)^2}{\frac{\phi}{K_{fM}} + \frac{1 - \phi}{K_m} - \frac{K_{DR}}{K_m^2}} \quad (8)$$

(where subscript M stands for monitor) to obtain the bulk modulus of the rock at the corresponding time step. From this computed modulus, drained shear modulus and computed density, the bulk rock density as well as P- and S-wave velocities at each time step are computed with usual equations

$$\rho_M = (1 - \phi)\rho_m + \phi\rho_f, \quad V_P = \left(\frac{K_M + \frac{4}{3}\mu}{\rho_M} \right)^{1/2}, \quad V_S = \left(\frac{\mu}{\rho_M} \right)^{1/2}, \quad (9)$$

where ρ_m denotes mineral density. The resulting changes of velocities and densities for each time step are shown in Figure 6.

5 SEISMIC SIMULATIONS

We use MIT OASES software to perform the simulations, which allows for realistic simulations, including a full range of multiples, but restricts to the 1D model of elastic properties.

To perform the simulations, we downsample the log data (including the results of rock physics modelling) to form 2 m thick layers using Backus averaging (Backus 1962).

The initial elastic model and the perturbation for each slow time step are shown in Figure 5 and Figure 6, respectively.

Figure 5: The baseline model of elastic properties for the synthetic well

Figure 6: Perturbation to the initial model of elastic properties for each time step

5.1 Seismic simulations – surface and VSP geometries

In order to generate synthetic seismograms, we use the following approach, which should provide us with a dataset suitable for both surface and downhole seismic data analysis. We place receivers in a well (0-1910 m MD) with 10 m increments. Sources are placed on the surface at distances from the well in the range of 10-2985 m with 25 m increments. This gives us an opportunity to:

- isolate only receivers at the zero depth (for surface seismic data analysis);
- select several source offsets while using the entire range of the receivers in the well to simulate offset VSP geometry
- use a subset of receivers in the well and the full range of sources, giving the walk-away VSP geometry.

We use two different setups for the source type and presence of the free surface:

- The top boundary of the model is set to free surface, while the source acts as a vertical force applied to this surface
- The top boundary was replaced with a homogeneous hemispace and source acting as an expansion centre (aka explosive source)

The reason for computing the two datasets is to simplify surface seismic data analysis by removing ground roll and source-generated S wave by excluding the free surface Figure 7.

Figure 7: Raw synthetic surface seismic gather. A - explosives, homogeneous hemispace at the top of the model, B - free surface and vertical force

All synthetic seismograms are generated with Ricker wavelet with 50 Hz central frequency.

A full set of seismograms is generated for each outputted flow simulation step (21 vintages, from 2028/01/01 to 2029/09/01 with one-month time increments). Below, we analyse a subset of those.

5.2 Zero-offset and offset VSP geometries

First, we explore time-lapse signals for zero-offset and offset VSP geometries. Zero-offset and offset VSP geometry assumes that the receivers are covering (usually) the entire well, while the number of source positions is limited to just a few. Zero-offset VSP means the distance between the source and the well is much smaller than the depth of the well; offset VSP geometry assumes the distance between the well and the source location is larger but still usually does not exceed the well depth.

The reason to start from this configuration is that borehole seismic usually could detect significantly smaller time-lapse signals than surface seismic (Pevzner et al. 2021). In

addition to that, borehole geometry allows us to understand the nature of that signal better as it deals with both downgoing and upgoing wavefield.

- Time-lapse signal in VSP data can be detected in one of these three forms:
- Changes in reflectivity from the target horizon
- Delays in the arrival of the direct wave at the receivers below the plume
- Changes in amplitude inside the plume due to the changes in impedance of the medium.

Figure 8 shows time-lapse VSP seismograms for 10m, 1010 m and 2010 m offsets at the end of injection. Panels from left to right represent baseline, monitor, difference * 5 and NRMS panels. NRMS was computed using a 60 ms sliding window. In general, NRMS difference exceeds 15-20% for zero-offset and 30-40% for offset VSP configurations. This is comparable to or slightly above the repeatability levels achievable by conventional VSP surveys with geophones or DAS sensors (Pevzner et al. 2011, Isaenkov et al. 2022) and likely to be detectable on the time-lapse data.

Note that we model the plume as an infinite layer, and at the early stages of injection, limited lateral size will play a role (Al Hosni et al. 2016, Pevzner et al. 2022).

Figure 8: Time-lapse VSP data for 10m, 1010 m and 2010 m offsets at the end of injection. Panels from left to right represent baseline, monitor, difference * 5 and NRMS panels.

Assuming we can get downhole receivers located inside and underneath the plume, we can analyse the time delays and amplitude changes caused by the injection using zero-offset VSP data as described in (Pevzner et al. 2022). After resampling the data to 0.01 ms and automated picking of the direct arrivals on VSP data, we estimate the time delay on the receives underneath the plume and amplitude anomalies caused by the softening of the medium due to the CO₂ injection (Figure 9). At the end of injection, the maximum time delay is expected to reach ~0.15 ms, and the amplitude anomaly inside of the plume will exceed 20%. This is comparable to the signal levels reported by (Pevzner et al. 2022) and likely to be detectable.

Amplitude and time delay analysis:

Figure 9: Amplitude and time delay analysis

5.3 Walk-away VSP geometry

Walk-away VSP (as well as 3D VSP) is a geometry where a number of source positions being acquired are significant, and they are either located along one or several 2D lines (walk-away VSP) or covering area and allowing to form full 3D volume (3D VSP). In the case of the use of conventional geophone arrays, the downhole array used for the survey is likely to be limited and cover only a small portion of the well.

Providing offset VSP is likely to be a feasible option for monitoring the plume, walk-away and 3D VSP geometries are also should be a viable option. While 1.5D simulations do not provide enough information to optimise the location of the tool in the well, we believe the level of time-lapse signal is sufficient to be detectable with either a well instrumented with fibre optic sensors or a conventional VSP tool string. Optimisation of the tool string location requires the exact tool parameters. However, providing the plume is around 400 m in the N-W direction, the top level of the tool string will have to be relatively shallow.

A few examples of synthetic time-lapse walk-away VSP gathers are shown in Figure 10 for 500, 1000 and 1500 m receiver levels at the end of injection. The biggest relative time-lapse anomaly is observed for the 1500 m level, which is located only ~100 m above the plume.

Figure 10: Synthetic walk-away VSP gathers for 500, 1000 and 1500 m receiver levels

5.4 Surface seismic

An example of the raw synthetic time-lapse gather is shown in Figure 11. As surface seismic has a bigger distance from the target horizon as compared to VSP data, the same trend observed on walk-away seismograms continues, with NRMS values further declining to ~20%.

Figure 11: Surface seismic time-lapse gather (end of injection)

Instead of processing synthetic surface seismic seismograms to simulate stacked section, we will use corridor stack trace derived from VSP data analysis, as described below.

Zero-offset VSP data processing to simulate surface seismic response

A typical role of the zero offset VSP surveys is to provide so-called corridor stack traces – a very reliable proxy for the best practically achievable trace mimicking the surface seismic stacked (migrated) trace along the well trajectory with multiples suppressed by selecting the corridor.

Here, we perform the zero-offset VSP data processing to obtain this corridor stack trace for each vintage and evaluate the magnitude of the time-lapse signal.

Figure 12 shows the raw synthetic zero-offset VSP seismogram.

Figure 12: Raw zero-offset VSP record (baseline), explosive source, no free surface

In order to obtain the corridor stack trace, we first remove the downgoing P-waves by 2D spatial filter (21 trace, alpha-trimmed mean, 50% rejection) and downgoing PS waves using the same filter parameters and corresponding travel time curve. The result is shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Zero-offset VSP seismogram, isolated reflected waves

Then, we apply normal moveout correction; the result is shown in Figure 14 and isolate the corridor along the TWTT curve by muting the portion of the wavefield likely to be contributed by multiples Figure 15.

Figure 14: Zero-offset VSP seismogram, upgoing PP waves after NMO correction

Figure 15: Zero-offset VSP seismogram, NMO corrected with isolated waves for corridor stacking

Series of the corridor stack traces produced for each vintage of time-lapse data are shown in figures Figure 16 and (zoomed in) Figure 17. One can see that the maximum change in amplitude is ~15%, with most of the changes occurring in the first five months of the start of injection. In reality (Figure 2), the configuration of the plume will keep changing for another half a year due to the lateral spread of the plume.

Figure 16: Corridor stack trace for each vintage. The red line represents the target horizon, and the graph at the top represents the target reflection's normalised (by baseline) amplitude.

Figure 17: Corridor stack trace for each vintage (zoom). The red line represents the target horizon, and the graph at the top represents the normalised (by baseline) amplitude of the target reflection.

5.5 Feasibility of the cross-hole seismic option

One of the main limitations of the cross-hole seismic is the limited power of the downhole seismic sources. As such, this technique might be suitable in cases where the distance between the pairs of wells that can be used to deploy seismic sources and receivers should be limited. Fortunately, the portion of the Zarusice field used for CCS is relatively small, with the plume size not exceeding $\sim 300 \times 600$ m with a number of relatively vertical wells with limited offsets from each other. In particular, wells ZA3, ZA4, ZA4A and ZA6 have a range of offsets (at the target horizon) between ~ 170 and ~ 600 m and can be the basis for the cross-hole monitoring (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Location of slightly deviated wells drilled at the site with respect to the CO₂ plume at the end of injection

To conduct a simplified modelling of this scenario using 1.5D OASES software, we use the following parameters:

- distance between source and receiver wells is 500 m;
- receivers are located from 0 to 2000 m with 10 m spacing;
- sources are located from 1600 m to 2000 m with 20 m spacing;
- we use a Ricker wavelet with a 50 Hz central frequency;
- source type – explosive;
- only the pre-injection and post-injection vintages were simulated (as we use 1.5 D modelling, we cannot factor lateral growth of the plume at the earlier stages).

In reality, downhole sources can generate much higher frequencies, but in this study, we evaluate the travel time changes for direct arrival times, so the frequency content is not very irrelevant.

Figure 19 and Figure 20 show an example of a synthetic seismogram for source depth at 1200 m and 1600 m depth, respectively.

Figure 19: An example of the synthetic seismogram for the 500 m distance between the wells and the source located at 1200 m depth (A – baseline, B – monitor, C – difference)

Figure 20: An example of the synthetic seismogram for the 500 m distance between the wells and the source located at 1600 m depth (A – baseline, B – monitor, C – difference)

In order to evaluate the magnitude of the time delays associated with the CO₂ plume, we performed manual picking of the direct wave arrival times for the traces where this wave is coming in first arrivals. For subhorizontal rays originating for the pairs of sources and receivers located at the waveguide at ~1300-1700 m, head waves are likely to come in first arrivals; traces corresponding to these rays were omitted.

The indicative ray coverage after the first break picking is shown in Figure 21, where 10% of the rays are shown (assuming straight rays and ignoring the refraction). Source locations are shown in red, and receiver locations are shown in blue.

Figure 21: Ray coverage after the first arrival picking. Only 10% of the rays displayed, refraction ignored.

Figure 22 shows the time delays caused by the CO₂ injection. In general, they do not exceed 1.1 ms. In order to perform time-lapse travel time tomography, the precision of the time picking should be significantly higher than the maximum time delay, e.g. the repeatability of the data should allow to achieve precision of the arrival time picking better than 0.1 ms. Without using permanent source and receiver arrays, this is probably not achievable.

Figure 22: Time delays of the direct wave arrival associated with CO₂ injection

6 DISCUSSION

6.1 Simulation, not prediction

This feasibility study is performed using a standard approach, where the results of the flow simulations are converted to synthetic seismograms using rock physics modelling followed by seismic modelling. All of these steps are prone to a high degree of uncertainty, starting from flow simulations. Both the actual geometry of the real plume,

its thickness, and the elastic properties of rocks can be different from what was used for simulations. This should be factored into the design of the actual monitoring system.

6.2 Surface seismic vs vertical seismic profiling, limitations of the 1.5D approach

Seismic simulations were performed using a 1.5D approach, where a laterally infinite layer replaced the plume. Assuming the depth of the target reflector being ~1600 m, a P-wave velocity of ~4000 m/s and central frequency of 50 Hz (which is possible for VSP and unlikely for surface seismic), the radius of the first Fresnel zone (for surface seismic) will be around 250 m. The plume is reaching a lateral size comparable to the Fresnel zone only at the end of injection. This means that the amplitude of the time-lapse signal is likely to be significantly smaller than predicted at the beginning of the injection.

The current estimation of the time-lapse signal for surface seismic is <15% NRMS computed using a 60 ms window. This means that the surface seismic is likely inefficient at the early stages of the injection. Typical NRMS values for the 3D land surveys are >20-30%, where the data is acquired using conventional seismic re-deployable systems (Pevzner et al. 2011, Lüth et al. 2011). To achieve higher repeatability on land permanently buried geophone systems can be used (Pevzner et al. 2017, Jarvis et al. 2018), however, there are no published examples of the land datasets with NRMS being significantly less than 15%. As such, surface seismic is unlikely to be a viable option for this project.

In general, downhole seismic surveys, regardless of the geometry and hardware, have a higher degree of repeatability and, if the receivers are located close to the target horizon, do not have a large penalty because of the relation between the lateral plume extend and the Fresnel zone.

An example of 4D VSP acquired with geophones located ~500 m above the target horizon is published by Pevzner et al. (2015). NRMS values for VSP data were < 15%. Offset VSP with re-deployable geophones (AlNasser et al. 2017) and (Pevzner et al. 2011), allowed to achieve NRMS of ~20%. VSP acquired with distributed acoustic sensing was sufficient to image CO₂ injection into the formation with residual gas (Yavuz et al. 2021).

The important benefit of the VSP geometries is the possibility to deploy the receivers deeper than the injection interval, allowing for the precise travel time and amplitude analysis (with the simulated levels of time-lapse signal being detectable).

The downside of the VSP geometry is limited coverage. This includes the possibility to generate only 2D transects for offset VSP configurations or limited volumes for 3D/4D VSP.

Providing the main goal of seismic monitoring here is to deliver the image of the plume, borehole geometry is likely to be preferable.

6.3 Potential hardware realisations and acquisition geometries, intervention vs PRM

Figure 1 shows the relative location of the reservoir, plume and several wells drilled in the field. The most logical solution would be to access one of the wells (preferably more or less vertical and drilled in the plume's centre, like ZA4H) and use it to deploy seismic receivers. If the well is open, conventional geophones can be used as an option. The other obvious type of receiver is the optical cable, which can be used to conduct distributed acoustic sensing. If the well is slightly deviated, suspended tubing encapsulated or a wireline cable would deliver the necessary coupling.

If the well has production tubing, re-completing the well by installing fibre optic cable on the production tubing would be the optimal solution. Getting access to more than one well should also be considered.

As the simulated plume has limited lateral extends, roughly 600x300 m or 400 x 200 m at a depth of ~1600 m, it should be possible to utilise the range of source position offsets up to 1000-1600 m away from the well to get the entire plume image. The general scheme showing the offset VSP image extension is shown in Figure 23. Maximum offset usually should be less than the depth of the well.

Figure 23. Offset VSP image extend

Several projects globally, including the CO2CRC Otway project (Pevzner et al. 2021), and Aquistore (White et al. 2021) used a combination of offset VSP geometry (to provide a rapid way of acquiring the data) with 4D VSP surveys to obtain the full 3D image of the plume, yet much more sparsely in time. We believe this should be a good proxy for the injection in the Zarosice field.

A permanent installation of the DAS cable in the well would provide an opportunity to conduct frequent offset VSP surveys (with permanent sources or conventional

vibroseis trucks). Ideally, the cable should be connected to a dedicated DAS interrogator with continuous data acquisition. If previously DAS units were relatively expensive, now there is a selection of reasonably priced devices.

The other benefit of the permanent installation is the possibility of monitoring the induced seismicity.

6.4 Time-lapse cross-hole surveys

The main reasons to perform time-lapse cross-hole surveys are the possibility of employing time-lapse travel time tomography and increasing the resolution of the image by using higher frequency sources. One of the requirements for this approach to be feasible is the availability of the pairs of wells located at distances not exceeding a few hundred meters, as downhole sources have significantly lower power as compared to sources that can be deployed on land. The Zarosice field has several legacy wells that can be used for this purpose; they have to be open and accessible for both source and receiver strings.

Performed simulations demonstrate that the expected magnitude of the time delays caused by the CO₂ injection for this geometry does not exceed ~1 ms, which makes it challenging to attempt travel time tomography with re-deployable downhole equipment. However, the potential increase of the vertical resolution in images obtained from the reflected wave analysis still can justify the use of cross-hole imaging. The strong factor supporting this is the successful deployment of cross-hole imaging in similar projects (Ajo-Franklin et al. 2013, Gupta et al. 2020).

7 CONCLUSION

The feasibility study of seismic monitoring in the Zarosice field allowed us to arrive at the following conclusions:

- Surface seismic monitoring of the CO₂ injection into the depleted oil and gas reservoir has limited chances of imaging the plume because of the small time-lapse signal level. However, surface seismic might be used to conduct assurance monitoring (absence of leakage in the overburden);
- Borehole seismic is likely to be useful in detecting and imaging the plume (because of the higher degree of repeatability); DAS receivers are the preferred option;
- A combination of offset VSPs (potentially with permanent sources) and 4D VSP are the preferred set of geometries;
- Application of cross-hole time-lapse seismic technique is feasible. However, the main motivation to use it is likely related to the imaging of the plume using reflected waves rather than travel time tomography.

REFERENCES

- Ajo-Franklin, J.B., Peterson, J., Doetsch, J. & Daley, T.M. 2013. High-resolution characterisation of a CO₂ plume using crosswell seismic tomography: Cranfield, MS, USA. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 18, 497-509.
- Al Hosni, M., Caspari, E., Pevzner, R., Daley, T.M. & Gurevich, B. 2016. Case History: Using time-lapse vertical seismic profiling data to constrain velocity–saturation relations: the Frio brine pilot CO₂ injection. *Geophysical Prospecting* 64, 987-1000.
- AlNasser, H., Pevzner, R., Tertyshnikov, K., Popik, D. & Urosevic, M. Year. Application of 4D VSP for Monitoring Of Small-Scale Supercritical CO₂ Injection: Stage 2C of CO₂CRC Otway Project Case Study. Conference Application of 4D VSP for Monitoring Of Small-Scale Supercritical CO₂ Injection: Stage 2C of CO₂CRC Otway Project Case Study, Abu-Dhabi, UAE, Expanded abstracts, BGP15.
- Backus, G.E. 1962. Long-Wave Elastic Anisotropy Produced by Horizontal Layering. *J. Geophys. Res.* 67, 4427-4440.
- Batzle, M. & Wang, Z. 1992. Seismic properties of pore fluids. *Geophysics* 57, 1396-1408.
- Couëslan, M.L., Smith, V., El-Kaseeh, G., Gilbert, J., Preece, N., Zhang, L. & Gulati, J. 2014. Development and implementation of a seismic characterisation and CO₂ monitoring program for the Illinois Basin – Decatur Project. *Greenhouse Gases: Science and Technology* 4, 626-644.
- Egorov, A., Pevzner, R., Bóna, A., Glubokovskikh, S., Puzyrev, V., Tertyshnikov, K. & Gurevich, B. 2017. Time-lapse full waveform inversion of vertical seismic profile data: Workflow and application to the CO₂CRC Otway project. *Geophysical Research Letters* 44, 7211-7218.
- Eiken, O., Ringrose, P., Hermanrud, C., Nazarian, B., Torp, T.A. & Høier, L. 2011. Lessons learned from 14 years of CCS operations: Sleipner, In Salah and Snøhvit. *Energy Procedia* 4, 5541-5548.
- Gupta, N., Kelley, M. & Kolb, C. 2020. Cross-Well Seismic Monitoring of CO₂ Injected Into the A-1 Carbonate and Brown Niagaran Formations at the Chester 16 Reef.
- Harris, K. 2017. The Use of Distributed Acoustic Sensing for 4D Monitoring Using Vertical Seismic Profiles: Results from the Aquistore CO₂ Storage Project. In: *Department of Earth Sciences*, pp. 160. Carleton University.
- Isaenkov, R., Pevzner, R., Glubokovskikh, S., Yavuz, S., Shashkin, P., Yurikov, A., Tertyshnikov, K., Gurevich, B., Correa, J., Wood, T., Freifeld, B. & Barraclough, P. 2022. Advanced time-lapse processing of continuous DAS VSP data for plume evolution monitoring: Stage 3 of the CO₂CRC Otway project case study. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 119, 103716.
- Ivandic, M., Juhlin, C., Lüth, S., Bergmann, P., Kashubin, A., Sopher, D., Ivanova, A., Baumann, G. & Hennings, J. 2015. Geophysical monitoring at the Ketzin pilot site for CO₂ storage: New insights into the plume evolution. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 32, 90-105.

- Jervis, M., Bakulin, A. & Smith, R. 2018. Making time-lapse seismic work in a complex desert environment for CO₂ EOR monitoring — Design and acquisition. *The Leading Edge* 37, 598-606.
- Kunz, O. & Group, E.G.R. 2007. *The GERG-2004 Wide Range Equation of State for Natural Gases and Other Mixtures: GERG TM15 2007*. VDI-Verlag, ISBN 9783183557066.
- Lawton, D.C., Osadetz, K.G. & Saeedfar, A. 2017. CCS Monitoring Technology Innovation at the CaMI Field Research Station, Alberta, Canada.
- Lumley, D. 2010. 4D seismic monitoring of CO₂ sequestration. *The Leading Edge* 29, 150-155.
- Lüth, S., Bergmann, P., Cosma, C., Enescu, N., Giese, R., Götz, J., Ivanova, A., Juhlin, C., Kashubin, A., Yang, C. & Zhang, F. 2011. Time-lapse seismic surface and down-hole measurements for monitoring CO₂ storage in the CO₂SINK project (Ketzin, Germany). *Energy Procedia* 4, 3435-3442.
- Mavko, G., Mukerji, T. & Dvorkin, J. 2009. *The Rock Physics Handbook: Tools for Seismic Analysis of Porous Media*. Cambridge University Press.
- Michael, K., Avijegon, A., Ricard, L., Myers, M., Tertyshnikov, K., Pevzner, R., Strand, J., Hortle, A., Stalker, L., Pervukhina, M., Harris, B., Feitz, A., Pejčić, B., Larcher, A., Rachakonda, P., Freifeld, B., Woitt, M., Langhi, L., Dance, T., Myers, J., Roberts, J., Saygin, E., White, C. & Seyyedi, M. 2020. A controlled CO₂ release experiment in a fault zone at the In-Situ Laboratory in Western Australia. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 99, 103100.
- Pevzner, R., Caspari, E., Urosevic, M., Shulakova, V. & Gurevich, B. 2015. 4D VSP Monitoring of CO₂ Sequestration into a Depleted Gas Reservoir, CO₂CRC Otway Project. In: *Carbon Dioxide Capture for Storage in Deep Geologic Formations – Results from the CO₂ Capture Project*, Vol. 4 (CCS Technology Development and Demonstration Results (2009-2014)) (ed. K.F. Gerdes), pp. 627-650. CPL Press, ISBN 978-1-872691-68-8.
- Pevzner, R., Glubokovskikh, S., Isaenkov, R., Shashkin, P., Tertyshnikov, K., Yavuz, S., Gurevich, B., Correa, J., Wood, T. & Freifeld, B. 2022. Monitoring subsurface changes by tracking direct-wave amplitudes and traveltimes in continuous distributed acoustic sensor VSP data. *Geophysics* 87, A1-A6.
- Pevzner, R., Isaenkov, R., Yavuz, S., Yurikov, A., Tertyshnikov, K., Shashkin, P., Gurevich, B., Correa, J., Glubokovskikh, S., Wood, T., Freifeld, B. & Barraclough, P. 2021. Seismic monitoring of a small CO₂ injection using a multi-well DAS array: Operations and initial results of Stage 3 of the CO₂CRC Otway project. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 110, 103437.
- Pevzner, R., Shulakova, V., Kepic, A. & Urosevic, M. 2011. Repeatability analysis of land time-lapse seismic data: CO₂CRC Otway pilot project case study. *Geophysical Prospecting* 59, 66-77.
- Pevzner, R., Urosevic, M., Popik, D., Shulakova, V., Tertyshnikov, K., Caspari, E., Correa, J., Dance, T., Kepic, A., Glubokovskikh, S., Ziramov, S., Gurevich, B., Singh, R., Raab, M., Watson, M., Daley, T., Robertson, M. & Freifeld, B. 2017. 4D surface seismic tracks small supercritical CO₂ injection into the subsurface: CO₂CRC Otway Project. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 63, 150-157.

- Phythian, P., Rive, M., Walton, C. & Scoby-Smith, L. 2023. Overview of the Barrow Island Land Seismic Acquisition and 4D Processing of the First Gorgon CO₂ Time-Lapse Monitor. In: *AEGC 2023, Australasian Exploration Geoscience Conference 2023*, pp. 1-7. AEGC.
- Saito, H., Nobuoka, D., Azuma, H., Xue, Z. & Tanase, D. 2006. Time-Lapse Crosswell Seismic Tomography for Monitoring Injected CO₂ in an Onshore Aquifer, Nagaoka, Japan. *Exploration Geophysics* 37, 30-36.
- Tertyshnikov, K., Egorov, A., Pevzner, R. & Bona, A. Year. Offset VSP for the Reservoir Monitoring. Conference Offset VSP for the Reservoir Monitoring, Abu-Dhabi, UAE, Expanded abstracts, BGP13.
- White, D., Bellefleur, G., Dodds, K. & Movahedzadeh, Z. 2021. Toward improved distributed acoustic sensing sensitivity for surface-based reflection seismics: Configuration tests at the Aquistore CO₂ storage site. *Geophysics* 87, P1-P14.
- White, D., Harris, K., Roach, L.A.N. & Robertson, M. 2019. 7 years of 4D seismic monitoring at the Aquistore CO₂ storage site, Saskatchewan, Canada. In: *SEG Technical Program Expanded Abstracts 2019*, pp. 4918-4922.
- Yavuz, S., Isaenkov, R., Pevzner, R., Gurevich, B., Tertyshnikov, K., Yurikov, A., Correa, J., Wood, T. & Freifeld, B. 2021. Processing of multi-well offset vertical seismic profile data acquired with distributed acoustic sensors and surface orbital vibrators: Stage 3 of the CO₂CRC Otway Project case study. *Geophysical Prospecting* 69, 1664-1677.
- Yurikov, A., Tertyshnikov, K., Yavuz, S., Shashkin, P., Isaenkov, R., Sidenko, E., Glubokovskikh, S., Barraclough, P. & Pevzner, R. 2022. Seismic monitoring of CO₂ geosequestration using multi-well 4D DAS VSP: Stage 3 of the CO₂CRC Otway project. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control* 119, 103726.
- Zhu, X. & McMechan, G.A. 1990. Direct estimation of the bulk modulus of the frame in a fluid-saturated elastic medium by Biot Theory. In: *SEG Technical Program Expanded Abstracts 1990*, pp. 787-790.

This report is a result of the CO₂-SPICER project
(CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir) - project No: TO01000112.

The CO₂-SPICER project benefits from a €2.32 mil. grant
from Norway and Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.

More information about the project can be found at
co2-spicer.geology.cz.

PROJECT PARTNERS

COORDINATOR

T A
Č R
